

Supplementary figures and tables for:

Identification of a novel HKU4-related coronavirus in single-cell datasets and clade viral host analysis

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Supplementary Figures and Tables

Phylogenetic Analysis

Supp. Fig. 1. HKU4-related CoV RdRp maximum likelihood tree. Tree drawn to scale, with branch lengths measured in the number of substitutions per site, bootstrap values >70% are shown. Tree rooted on midpoint and displayed using MEGA11. Accession numbers and names in Supp. Info. 3.

Supp. Fig. 2. Maximum likelihood tree of spike gene. Tree drawn to scale, with branch lengths measured in the number of substitutions per site, bootstrap values >70% are shown. Tree rooted on midpoint and displayed using MEGA11. Accession numbers and names in Supp. Info. 3.

Supp. Fig. 3. Maximum likelihood tree of spike protein sequences of 14 HKU4-related CoVs, HKU5, and MERS. Tree drawn to scale, with branch lengths measured in the number of substitutions per site, bootstrap values >70% are shown. Tree rooted on midpoint and displayed using MEGA11. Accession numbers and names in Supp. Info. 3.

Supp. Fig. 4. HKU4-related CoV N gene maximum likelihood tree. Tree drawn to scale, with branch lengths measured in the number of substitutions per site, bootstrap values >70% are shown. Tree rooted on midpoint and displayed using MEGA11. Accession numbers and names in Supp. Info. 3.

Supp. Fig. 5. HKU4-related CoV ORF3-5 gene region maximum likelihood tree. Tree drawn to scale, with branch lengths measured in the number of substitutions per site, bootstrap values >70% are shown. Tree rooted on midpoint and displayed using MEGA11. Accession numbers and names in Supp. Info. 3.

Spike Protein

Supp. Fig. 6. Receptor binding motif section of spike protein after alignment of spike protein sequences with the highest homology to HKU4r-BGI-2020 (consensus reference numbering).

Supp. Fig. 7. 3D structure of the S1 domain of S protein of BtCoV HKU4 (purple) in complex with hDPP4 (dark green). Seventeen amino acids in the receptor binding motif of HKU4 with differences to HKU4r-BGI-2020 are highlighted in bright green.

	600	605	610	615	620	625	630	635	640	645	650	655	660	665	670																																																							
<i>HKU4r-BGI-2020</i>	S	V	C	P	M	L	D	L	G	N	S	S	T	X	X	X	X	G	K	C	V	D	X	S	L	X	G	V	T	X	R	G	X	F	Q	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	F	V	Y	D	S	F	D	N	L	V	G	Y	Y	S	D	D	G	N	Y	Y	C	V	R	P				
<i>GX/HKU4-GX/2020</i>	S	V	C	P	M	L	D	L	G	N	S	S	T	T	H	Y	L	G	K	C	V	D	Y	S	L	Y	G	V	T	G	R	G	V	F	Q	N	C	T	A	V	G	I	R	Q	R	F	V	Y	D	S	F	D	N	L	V	G	Y	Y	S	D	D	G	N	Y	Y	C	V	R	P	
<i>MJHKU4r-CoV-1</i>	S	V	C	P	M	L	D	L	G	N	S	S	T	T	H	Y	L	G	K	C	V	D	Y	S	L	Y	G	V	T	G	R	G	V	F	Q	N	C	T	A	V	G	I	R	Q	R	F	V	Y	D	S	F	D	N	L	V	G	Y	Y	S	D	D	G	N	Y	Y	C	V	R	P	
<i>HKU4/P251T/panqilin/2018</i>	S	V	C	P	M	L	D	L	G	N	S	S	T	T	H	Y	L	G	K	C	V	D	Y	S	L	Y	G	V	T	G	R	G	V	F	Q	N	C	T	A	V	G	I	R	Q	R	F	V	Y	D	S	F	D	N	L	V	G	Y	Y	S	D	D	G	N	Y	Y	C	V	R	P	
<i>TpCoV 162275</i>	S	V	C	P	M	L	D	L	G	N	S	S	T	T	N	Q	L	G	K	C	V	D	Y	S	L	Y	G	V	T	G	R	G	V	F	Q	N	C	T	A	V	G	V	R	Q	Q	R	F	V	Y	D	S	F	D	N	L	V	G	Y	Y	S	D	D	G	N	Y	Y	C	V	R	P
<i>HKU4 25</i>	S	V	C	P	M	L	D	L	G	D	S	S	T	T	N	R	L	G	K	C	V	D	Y	S	L	Y	G	V	T	G	R	G	V	F	Q	N	C	T	A	V	G	V	K	Q	Q	R	F	V	Y	D	S	F	D	N	L	V	G	Y	Y	S	D	D	G	N	Y	Y	C	V	R	P
<i>TpCoV 161028</i>	S	V	C	P	M	L	D	L	G	D	S	S	T	T	N	R	L	G	K	C	V	D	Y	S	L	Y	G	V	T	G	R	G	V	F	Q	N	C	T	A	V	G	V	K	Q	Q	R	F	V	Y	D	S	F	D	N	L	V	G	Y	Y	S	D	D	G	N	Y	Y	C	V	R	P
<i>TpCoV 160081</i>	S	V	C	P	M	L	D	L	G	D	S	S	T	T	N	R	L	G	K	C	V	D	Y	S	L	Y	G	V	T	G	R	G	V	F	Q	N	C	T	A	V	G	V	K	Q	Q	R	F	V	Y	D	S	F	D	N	L	V	G	Y	Y	S	D	D	G	N	Y	Y	C	V	R	P
<i>HKU4 SZ140324</i>	S	V	C	P	M	L	D	L	G	D	S	S	T	T	N	R	L	G	K	C	V	D	Y	S	L	Y	G	V	T	G	R	G	V	F	Q	N	C	T	A	V	G	V	K	Q	Q	R	F	V	Y	D	S	F	D	N	L	V	G	Y	Y	S	D	D	G	N	Y	Y	C	V	R	P
<i>HKU4 GZ1862</i>	S	V	C	P	M	L	D	L	G	E	S	S	T	T	N	R	L	G	K	C	V	D	Y	S	L	Y	G	V	T	G	R	G	V	F	Q	N	C	T	A	V	G	V	K	Q	Q	R	F	V	Y	D	S	F	D	N	L	V	G	Y	Y	S	D	D	G	N	Y	Y	C	V	R	P
<i>HKU4 GZ131656</i>	S	V	C	P	M	L	D	L	G	D	S	S	T	T	N	R	L	G	K	C	V	D	Y	S	L	Y	G	V	T	G	R	G	V	F	Q	N	C	S	A	V	G	I	K	Q	Q	R	F	V	Y	D	S	F	D	N	L	V	G	Y	Y	S	D	D	G	N	Y	Y	C	V	R	P
<i>TpCoV 160079</i>	S	V	C	P	M	L	D	L	G	D	S	S	T	T	N	R	L	G	K	C	V	D	Y	S	L	Y	G	V	T	G	R	G	V	F	Q	N	C	T	A	V	G	V	K	Q	Q	R	F	V	Y	D	S	F	D	N	L	V	G	Y	Y	S	D	D	G	N	Y	Y	C	V	R	P
<i>HKU4-2 B05f</i>	S	V	C	P	M	L	D	L	G	D	S	S	T	T	N	R	L	G	K	C	V	D	Y	S	L	Y	G	V	T	G	R	G	V	F	Q	N	C	T	A	V	G	V	K	Q	Q	R	F	V	Y	D	S	F	D	N	L	V	G	Y	Y	S	D	D	G	N	Y	Y	C	V	R	P
<i>HKU4 SM3A</i>	S	V	C	P	M	L	D	L	G	D	S	S	T	T	N	R	L	G	K	C	V	D	Y	S	L	Y	G	V	T	G	R	G	V	F	Q	N	C	S	A	V	G	V	K	Q	Q	R	F	V	Y	D	S	F	D	N	L	V	G	Y	Y	S	D	D	G	N	Y	Y	C	V	R	P
<i>HKU4r-HZAU-2020</i>	S	V	C	P	M	L	D	L	G	E	S	S	T	T	N	R	L	G	K	C	V	D	Y	S	L	Y	G	V	T	G	R	G	V	F	Q	N	C	T	A	V	G	V	K	Q	Q	R	F	V	Y	D	S	F	D	N	L	V	G	Y	Y	S	D	D	G	N	Y	Y	C	V	R	P
<i>BtTp-BetaCoV/GX2012</i>	S	V	C	P	M	L	D	L	G	E	S	S	T	T	N	R	L	G	K	C	V	D	Y	S	L	Y	G	V	T	G	R	G	V	F	Q	N	C	T	A	V	G	V	K	Q	Q	R	F	V	Y	D	S	F	D	N	L	V	G	Y	Y	S	D	D	G	N	Y	Y	C	V	R	P
<i>HKU5 YD13403</i>	S	V	C	P	M	Q	A	L	R	N	D	T	S	E	D	K	L	D	V	C	V	E	Y	S	L	H	G	I	T	G	C	V	F	H	N	C	T	S	V	G	L	R	N	Q	R	F	V	Y	D	T	F	D	N	L	V	G	Y	H	S	D	N	G	N	Y	Y	C	V	R	P	
<i>MERS EMC/2012</i>	S	V	C	P	K	L	E	F	A	N	D	T	K	A	S	Q	L	G	N	C	V	E	Y	S	L	Y	G	V	S	G	R	G	V	F	Q	N	C	T	A	V	G	V	R	Q	Q	R	F	V	Y	D	A	Y	Q	N	L	V	G	Y	Y	S	D	D	G	N	Y	Y	C	L	R	A

Supp. Fig. 8. Amino acid positions 600-670 (consensus reference numbering) for alignment of spike protein sequences to HKU4r-BGI-2020. Includes coverage of RQQR putative furin cleavage motif (Chen et al., 2023) at positions 643-646.

Supp. Fig. 9. Alignment of spike protein sequences to HKU4r-BGI-2020 displaying amino acid positions 717-787 (consensus reference numbering) including MERS (RSVR) and HKU5 (RSAR) S1/S2 junction furin cleavage motifs at positions 765-768.

Supp. Fig. 10. Alignment of spike protein sequences to HKU4r-BGI-2020 displaying amino acid positions 855-925 (consensus reference numbering) including S2' MERS (RSAR) furin cleavage motif at positions 902-905.

Supp. Fig. 11. Alignment of spike protein sequences to HKU4r-BGI-2020 displaying amino acid positions 50-120 (consensus reference numbering). HKU4r-BGI-2020, PCoV HKU4-P251T, PCoV MjHKU4r-CoV-1 and *Tylonycteris robustula* bat CoV 162275 contain a three amino acid insert in the NTD of the S protein not found in other known HKU4-related CoV sequences, HKU5-CoV or MERS-CoV.

Supp. Fig. 12. 3D structure of the MERS-CoV S protein PDB: 7X27 viewed using Mol 3D viewer. Sequence GHA---TGT--T (AA positions 90-95, dashes indicating location of gaps relative to HKU4r-BGI-2020) in NTD of the S1 domain of the S protein highlighted in green. The three amino acid insert HTT in HKU4r-BGI-2020, PCoV HKU4-P251T, PCoV MjHKU4r-CoV-1 and YTT in TrCoV 162275 S protein sequences relative to other HKU4-related CoVs occurs in an external position of the structure.

Selection Pressure

Supp. Fig. 13. Cumulative dN/dS plots showing indels and stop codons for spike protein sequences for a) PCoV HKU4-P251T and TrCoV 162275; b) MjHKU4r-CoV-1 and TrCoV 162275; and c) HKU4-BGI-2020 and TrCoV 162275, plotted using SNAP (Korber, 2002). Missing amino acid sections in HKU4-BGI-2020 are located at positions 185-203; 404-420; 528-557; 574-583; 628-638; 856-869 and 976-1011.

Supp. Fig. 14. Cumulative dN/dS plots showing indels and stop codons for spike protein sequences from a) PCoV HKU4-P251T and HKU4r-BGI-2020; b) MjHKU4r-CoV-1 and HKU4r-BGI-2020; and c) PCoV HKU4-P251T and MjHKU4r-CoV-1. Plotted using SNAP (Korber, 2002). Missing amino acid sections in HKU4-BGI-2020 are located at positions 185-203; 404-420; 528-557; 574-583; 628-638; 856-869 and 976-1011.

Host analysis

Supp. Fig. 15. Mitochondrial alignments of selected datasets in BioProject PRJNA747757 to all mitochondrial genomes on NCBI using minimap2. A 50% genome coverage cutoff was applied prior to plotting.

Supp. Fig. 16. Percent of mitochondrial alignments of selected datasets in BioProject PRJNA747757 to all mitochondrial genomes on NCBI using minimap2 with a greater than 10% coverage. A 50% genome coverage cutoff was applied prior to plotting.

SRA	Sample name	Species	Mitochondrion	Accession	N	DATA(%)	Coverage%	Cov 30x %	HKU4r-CoV reads
SRR15199668	PGN_LG	Manis javanica	Capra aegagrus	NC_028161.1	144892	0.95	93.57	73.03	78
SRR15199660	CT_LG	Felis catus	Capra aegagrus	NC_028161.1	116089	0.41	91.58	70.87	
SRR15199656	DK_LG	Anas platyrhynchos	Capra aegagrus	NC_028161.1	222	2.78	25.03	0.54	
SRR15199675	CT_ES	Felis catus	Capra aegagrus	NC_028161.1	557	0	21.54	3.13	
SRR15199676	CT_ED	Felis catus	Capra aegagrus	NC_028161.1	113	0	15.33	0	
SRR15199657	DG_LG	Canis lupus familiaris	Capra aegagrus	NC_028161.1	340	60.07	14.2	0.61	
SRR15199661	CT_KY	Felis catus	Capra aegagrus	NC_028161.1	97	0	12.53	0	
SRR15199659	CT_LR	Felis catus	Capra aegagrus	NC_028161.1	39	0	11.6	0	
SRR15199655	GT_LG	Capra aegagrus	Columba livia	NC_013978.1	704	0.02	33.83	3.99	
SRR15199656	DK_LG	Anas platyrhynchos	Columba livia	NC_013978.1	51	0.64	12.3	0	
SRR15199672	PGN_DM	Manis javanica	Felis catus	NC_001700.1	148933	42.64	77.4	52.6	44
SRR15199667	PGN_LI	Manis javanica	Felis catus	NC_001700.1	231557	6.65	76.97	59.48	51558
SRR15199663	PGN_SN	Manis javanica	Felis catus	NC_001700.1	92020	14.51	75.05	47.02	
SRR15199670	PGN_HT	Manis javanica	Felis catus	NC_001700.1	47121	0.9	72.35	31.7	1
SRR15199671	PGN_ES	Manis javanica	Felis catus	NC_001700.1	24596	1.67	70.28	27.22	838
SRR15199669	PGN_KY	Manis javanica	Felis catus	NC_001700.1	4449	4.32	56.13	11.61	
SRR15199668	PGN_LG	Manis javanica	Felis catus	NC_001700.1	3806	0.03	43.01	9.33	78
SRR15199665	PGN_SH	Manis javanica	Felis catus	NC_001700.1	503	15.34	31.3	2.35	18
SRR15199666	PGN_LR	Manis javanica	Felis catus	NC_001700.1	406	16.32	22.26	1.46	7
SRR15199674	HR_LG	Mesocricetus auratus	Homo sapiens	NC_012920.1	58	23.97	15.19	0	
SRR15199673	LD_LG	Anolis carolinensis	Homo sapiens	NC_012920.1	103	0.02	10.1	0	
SRR15199675	CT_ES	Felis catus	Manis javanica isolate N	MG196309.1	40391	0.09	71.86	35.96	
SRR15199660	CT_LG	Felis catus	Manis javanica isolate N	MG196309.1	8136	0.03	70.83	18.8	
SRR15199676	CT_ED	Felis catus	Manis javanica isolate N	MG196309.1	11172	0.03	67.49	20.64	
SRR15199661	CT_KY	Felis catus	Manis javanica isolate N	MG196309.1	7218	0.01	62.36	16.42	
SRR15199664	CT_HT	Felis catus	Manis javanica isolate N	MG196309.1	3842	0.01	56.77	11.33	
SRR15199659	CT_LR	Felis catus	Manis javanica isolate N	MG196309.1	3175	0.02	54.57	9.8	
SRR15199655	GT_LG	Capra aegagrus	Sus scrofa	MK251046.1	2088	0.07	52.43	12.36	
SRR15199656	DK_LG	Anas platyrhynchos	Sus scrofa	MK251046.1	166	2.08	24.88	0	
SRR15199668	PGN_LG	Manis javanica	Sus scrofa	MK251046.1	118	0	22.21	0	78
SRR15199673	LD_LG	Anolis carolinensis	Sus scrofa	MK251046.1	141	0.02	18.72	0.09	
SRR15199657	DG_LG	Canis lupus familiaris	Sus scrofa	MK251046.1	121	21.38	18.72	0	

Supp. Table 1. Contaminating mitochondrial genomic sequences in selected NGS datasets in BioProject PRJNA747757, with DATA(%) indicating percentage of all mitochondrial alignments per SRA sample.

Contaminating Viruses

Supp. Fig. 17. Read count for reads matching viruses identified in BioProject PRJNA747757, using a virus minimum coverage of 10%. Displayed using a log scale.

Supp. Fig. 18. Per sample coverage percentage of viruses identified in BioProject PRJNA747757. A virus minimum coverage of 10% was used.

Host analysis of “clade b” HKU4-related CoVs

Supp. Fig. 19. Alignment of reads in NGS dataset for sample HKU4-GX (SRR22936420) in BioProject PRJNA901878 to MAG: Pangolin coronavirus HKU4 isolate GX/HKU4-GX/2020 (OQ297693.1). Aligned using minimap2, displayed using IGV.

Accession	N	Avg depth	Median	Coverage%	Cov 4x %	Cov 10x %	Cov 30x %	Cov 100x %
OQ297693.1	14404	71.06	68	100	99.98	99.84	99.07	11.25

Supp. Table 2. Read mapping statistics for alignment of HKU4-GX (SRR22936420) in BioProject PRJNA901878 to MAG: Pangolin coronavirus HKU4 isolate GX/HKU4-GX/2020.

Supp. Fig. 20. Mitochondrial alignments of 86 datasets in BioProject PRJNA901878 to all mitochondrial genomes on NCBI using minimap2. Only datasets with 50% genome coverage or greater are plotted.

Supp. Fig. 21. Mitochondrial alignments of selected datasets in BioProject PRJNA901878 to all mitochondrial genomes on NCBI using minimap2. A 50% genome coverage cutoff was applied prior to plotting.

Supp. Fig. 22. Percentage of total mitochondrial alignments of selected datasets in BioProject PRJNA901878 to all mitochondrial genomes on NCBI using minimap2. A 50% genome coverage cutoff was applied prior to plotting.

Supp. Fig. 23. *De novo* assembled contigs (top track) and reads in dataset HKU4-GX (SRR22936420) in BioProject PRJNA901878 aligning to the *Manis javanica* isolate T298 mitochondrial genome (NC_026781.1).

Supp. Fig. 24. Reads in NGS dataset for sample HKU4-GX (SRR22936420) in BioProject PRJNA901878 aligning to the *Sus scrofa taiwanensis* mitochondrial genome (NC_014692.1). Top track read depth scale is 0-67811. Average read depth is 515.49 with 100% genome coverage. Displayed in IGV with options to downsample reads and remove duplicates.

Supp. Fig. 25. *Rhizomys pruinusosus* and *Sus scrofa* genomic percentage content for reads and *de novo* assembled contigs in RNA-Seq dataset SRR22936497 from sample GX19-89 in BioProject PRJNA901878 using three independent methods.

Supp. Fig. 26. *De novo* assembled contigs for selected datasets in BioProject PRJNA901878 were filtered to include only those 300-nt or longer then aligned to *Manis javanica* and *Sus scrofa* genomes using three methods. Percentage of contigs best aligning to *M. javanica* or *S. scrofa* are shown in log scale.

Supp. Fig. 27. Alignment of four SRA datasets in BioProject PRJCA002517 containing HKU4-related CoVs to all mitochondrial genomes on NCBI. Only genomes with greater than 50 percent coverage are shown.

Supp. Fig. 28. Alignment of four CRA datasets in PRJCA002517 containing HKU4-related CoVs to all mitochondrial genomes on NCBI. Read counts were divided by total read counts matching mitochondrial

genomes where coverage was greater than 10% to give percentages shown. Only genomes with greater than 50 percent coverage are plotted.

Run	Sample	Isolate	N	Avg depth	Median	Cov 1x%	Cov 4x %	Cov 10x %	Cov 30x %	Cov 100x %
CRR477157	A100	MjHKU4r-CoV-4	64506	314.51	242	99.99	99.96	99.96	99.43	88.62
CRR477156	A98	MjHKU4r-CoV-3	701	3.41	3	83.89	37.54	5.49	0	0
CRR477155	A97	MjHKU4r-CoV-2	10062	49.03	37	99.96	99.22	94.61	62.09	9.64
CRR477154	A96	MjHKU4r-CoV-1	2538	12.18	11	99.13	92.56	57.05	2.38	0

Supp. Table 3 Summary statistics for read alignments to MjHKU4r-CoV-1 to 4 for four datasets in BioProject PRJCA002517.

Supp. Fig. 29. PRJCA002517 dataset full genome read alignments. Reads in four datasets documented as generated from pangolin samples (Shi et al., 2023) were aligned to full *Manis javanica*, *Homo sapiens*, and *Chlorocebus sabaues* genomes for using ConcatRef (Jo et al., 2017), Seal (Bushnell, 2022), and Disambiguate (Valentine, 2020) workflows. Percentages of reads mapping to each genome were plotted separately.

Supp. Fig. 30. PRJCA002517 dataset full genome contig alignments. *De novo* assembled contigs in four datasets documented as generated from pangolin samples (Shi et al., 2023) were aligned to full *Manis javanica*, *Homo sapiens*, and *Chlorocebus sabaeus* genomes for using ConcatRef (Jo et al., 2017), Seal (Bushnell, 2022), and Disambiguate (Valentine, 2020) workflows. Percentages of reads mapping to each genome were plotted separately.

Supp. Fig. 31. Maximum likelihood tree for full genomes for MjHKU4r-CoV-1 and variants and *Tylonycteris robustula* CoV 162275. Generated using MEGA11 using a GTR+I model with 100 bootstrap replicates. Tree drawn to scale, with branch lengths measured in the number of substitutions per site. Tree rooted on TrCoV 162275 and displayed using MEGA11. Bootstrap values >70% are shown, accession numbers and names in Supp. Info. 3.

